

EFFECT OF STRONTIUM DOPING ON THE STRUCTURAL AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF NiO NANOPARTICLES

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M E S Asmabi College
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Master of Science

In Physics

Submitted by

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July 2022

Student's Declaration

I, **MOHAMED SHAHIN T S**, hereby declare that the project work titled “**Effect of Strontium Doping on the Structural And Optical Properties of NiO Nanoparticles**” is the original work done by me under the guidance of **Dr. Sheena P A, Associate Professor, Department of Physics, M E S Asmabi College P. Vemballur** in partial fulfillment of requirements for the award of **Master of Science in Physics**. I also declare that this project work has not been submitted previously for the award of any degree or diploma earlier. The findings in the report are based on the information collected by me and not copied from elsewhere.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**Effect of Strontium Doping on the Structural And Optical Properties of NiO Nanoparticles**” is a bonafide record of work done by **Mohamed Shahin T S (AIAUMPH005)** at M E S Asmabi College P. Vemballur under the guidance of Dr. Sheena P A in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of Master of Science in Physics from University of Calicut during the period of March 2021 to July 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify the dissertation entitled “**Effect of Strontium Doping on the Structural And Optical Properties of NiO Nanoparticles**” is an authentic record of project work carried out by **Mohamed Shahin T S** of M E S Asmabi college P. Vemballur under the supervision in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Master of Science in Physics.

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Abstract

In the present work, the NiO nanoparticles are synthesized by chemical precipitation technique which is a cost effective and low temperature method. The first chapter gives a brief outline about nanotechnology its synthesis techniques and applications and NiO nanoparticles. It is followed by literature review of previous works in the area of NiO nanoparticles. The second chapter deals with the various characterization techniques used in this study. Results and analysis are discussed in the third chapter. And finally, in the last chapter gives a brief conclusion of the study.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The study of designing, creating, and using objects with dimensions of less than or equal to one billionth of a millimeter (100 nm) is known as nanoscience. Norio Taniguchi, a professor at Tokyo Science University, originally popularized the word "nanotechnology" in 1974 to refer to the expansion of conventional silicon machining into areas smaller than 1 micron. The word "nano" is derived from the Greek for dwarf, although in scientific parlance it refers to one billionth. A nm is one billionth, or 10^{-9} of a metre.

The essence of nanotechnology is therefore size and control. Nanomaterial is defined as the "material with any external dimension in the nanoscale or having internal structure or surface structure in the nanoscale", with nanoscale defined as the "length range approximately from 1 nm to 100 nm".

New properties appear as anything gets closer to the nanoscale because of size confinement, quantum phenomena, and coulomb blocking. Nanomaterials are significant because of their enormous surface area to volume ratio in comparison to bulk materials, as well as basic size effects. When the size of a material is reduced below 100 nm, its properties resemble several physical phenomena such as the mean free path of electrons, photons, light wavelength, and energy transfer distance. As a result, characteristics might deviate from bulk material values while remaining different from those investigated by quantum physics. Nano crystallites are nanoparticles having a well-organized arrangement of atoms (or ions). Nanomaterials are significant because of their enormous surface area to volume ratio in comparison to bulk materials, as well as basic size effects. As a material's size decreases below 100 nm, its properties become more comparable.

Size is largely a relative concept, but quantum mechanics defines absolute smallness. Quantum effects are required to comprehend some nano-objects, such as the microscopic clusters of atoms known as quantum dots, nano dots, or nanoparticles. These are microscopic spheres of a solid, most commonly a semiconductor. Electrons in condensed matter are no longer point particles; they are thought to be in free space, but have extension, as measured by their Bohr radius, which can range from a few to hundreds of nanometres

depending on the substance. It is feasible to manufacture nanoparticles smaller than the Bohr radius of the electrons contained inside them, resulting in quantum confinement, with the significant impact that the particle's optical absorption and fluorescence emission are shifted towards higher energies. Depending on the particle size we get the magnitude of shift.

1.2 Synthesis Methods of Nanoparticles

Nanomaterials are synthesized by different methods based on the types and nature of the nanomaterials. In a broad sense “top-down” and “bottom-up” are the two foremost methods to synthesize nanomaterials. In top-down method bulk materials have been reduced to nanomaterials, and in case of bottom-up method, the nanomaterials are synthesized from elementary level.

In top-down approach nano objects and materials are created by larger entities without involving its atomic reactions usually top-down approach are practiced less as compared to the bottom-up approach. In the bottom-up approach different materials are constructed from molecular components of their own which are not required to assemble by an external source. They chemically assemble themselves by recognizing the molecules of their own kind. Two or more components can be combined to form a new one or to be used as whole. Some of the examples of molecular self-assembly are Watson crick base pairing and enzyme substrate.

The different methods which are being used to synthesize nanomaterials are chemical vapor deposition method, coprecipitation, sonochemical spark, hydrothermal synthesis, pulsed laser ablation, microwave, sol-gel, biological synthesis & so on. The synthesis of metal nanocomposites includes spray pyrolysis, liquid infiltration, the rapid solidification process, high-energy ball milling, chemical vapor deposition, physical vapor deposition, and chemical processes such as sol-gel and colloidal. The synthesis of ceramic nanocomposites includes the powder process, polymer precursor process, and the sol-gel

process. Finally, the fabrication of polymer nanocomposites includes intercalation, in situ intercalative polymerization, melt intercalation, template synthesis, mixing, in situ polymerization, and the sol-gel process.

1.2.1 Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD)

Chemical vapor deposition is a deposition method having a great significance in the generation of carbon-based nanomaterials. In CVD, a thin film is formed on the substrate surface via the chemical reaction of vapor-phase precursors. A precursor is considered suitable for CVD if it has adequate volatility, high chemical purity, good stability during evaporation, low cost, a non-hazardous nature and a long shelf-life. Moreover, its decomposition should not result in residual impurities. However, the choice of catalyst plays a significant role in the morphology and type of nanomaterial obtained. Overall, CVD is an excellent method for producing high-quality nanomaterials, and it is well-known for the production of two-dimensional nanomaterials. Microfabrication processes widely use CVD to deposit materials in various forms, including monocrystalline, polycrystalline, amorphous, and epitaxial.

1.2.2 Solvothermal and Hydrothermal Methods

The hydrothermal process is one of the most well-known and extensively used methods used to produce nanostructured materials. In the hydrothermal method, nanostructured materials are attained through a heterogeneous reaction carried out in an aqueous medium at high pressure and temperature around the critical point in a sealed vessel. The solvothermal method is like the hydrothermal method. The only difference is that it is carried out in a non-aqueous medium. Hydrothermal and solvothermal methods are generally carried out in closed systems. The microwave-assisted hydrothermal method has recently received significant attention for engineering nanomaterials, combining the merits of both hydrothermal and microwave methods. Hydrothermal and solvothermal methods

are exciting and useful methods for producing various nano-geometries of materials, like nanowires, nanorods, nanosheets, and nanospheres.

1.2.3 Pulsed Laser Ablation

Laser ablation synthesis involves nanoparticle generation using a powerful laser beam that hits the target material. During the laser ablation process, the source material or precursor vaporizes due to the high energy of the laser irradiation, resulting in nanoparticle formation. Utilizing laser ablation for the generation of noble metal nanoparticles can be considered as a green technique, as there is no need for stabilizing agents or other chemicals. A wide range of nanomaterials can be produced through this technique, such as metal nanoparticles, carbon nanomaterials, oxide composites, and ceramics. Pulsed laser ablation in liquids is an exciting approach for producing monodisperse colloidal nanoparticle solutions without using surfactants or ligands. The nanoparticle properties, such as average size and distribution, can be tuned *via* adjusting the fluence, wavelength, and laser salt addition.

1.2.4 Coprecipitation

The co-precipitation method is an easy, economic, and simple technique to synthesize materials possessing different properties of technological importance. Using the co-precipitation technique, nanomaterials can be synthesized without extra agglomeration steps.

To synthesize a desired material using this technique, first the aqueous solution of the precursors is prepared under constant stirring and heating. Then, individual prepared solutions are mixed over constant heating and stirring for a certain amount of time. This process is an open-air process. After mixing, formed precipitates are filtered out via centrifugation. To obtain the nanomaterials in powder form, filtered-out precipitates are dried and calcinated at a specific temperature. Throughout the whole process, simultaneous nucleation, growth, coarsening, and agglomeration occur.

1.2.5 Microemulsion

Microemulsions are clear, thermodynamically stable isotropic liquid mixtures of oil, water and surfactant, frequently in combination with a cosurfactant. The aqueous phase may contain salt(s) and/or other ingredients, and the "oil" may actually be a complex mixture of different hydrocarbons. In contrast to ordinary emulsions, microemulsions form upon simple mixing of the components and do not require the high shear conditions generally used in the formation of ordinary emulsions.

1.2.6 Sonochemical Synthesis

Sonochemical synthesis is the process which utilizes the principles of sonochemistry to make molecules undergo a chemical reaction with the application of powerful ultrasound radiation (20 kHz–10 MHz). Sonochemistry generates hot spots that can achieve very high temperatures (5000–25.000 K), pressures of more than 1000 atmospheres, and rates of heating and cooling that can exceed 10^{11} K/s. High intensity ultrasound produces chemical and physical effects that can be used for the production or modification of a wide range of nanostructured materials. The principle that causes the modification of nanostructures in the sonochemical process is acoustic cavitation.

1.2.7 Sol-gel Method

The sol–gel method is a wet-chemical technique that is extensively used for the development of nanomaterials. This method is used for the development of various kinds of high-quality metal-oxide-based nanomaterials. During the synthesis of the metal-oxide nanoparticles, the liquid precursor is transformed to a sol, and the sol is ultimately converted into a network structure that is called a gel, since the method is known as sol-gel method. Conventional precursors for the generation of nanomaterials using the sol–gel method are metal alkoxides. The method is used for the fabrication of metal oxides, especially the oxides of silicon (Si) and titanium (Ti). The synthesis process of nanoparticles *via* the sol–gel method can be completed in several steps.

In this chemical procedure, a "sol" (a colloidal solution) is formed that then gradually evolves towards the formation of a gel-like diphasic system containing both a liquid phase

and solid phase whose morphologies range from discrete particles to continuous polymer networks. In the case of the colloid, the volume fraction of particles (or particle density) may be so low that a significant amount of fluid may need to be removed initially for the gel-like properties to be recognized. This can be accomplished in any number of ways. The simplest method is to allow time for sedimentation to occur, and then pour off the remaining liquid. Centrifugation can also be used to accelerate the process of phase separation.

Removal of the remaining liquid (solvent) phase requires a drying process, which is typically accompanied by a significant amount of shrinkage and densification. The rate at which the solvent can be removed is ultimately determined by the distribution of porosity in the gel. The ultimate microstructure of the final component will clearly be strongly influenced by changes imposed upon the structural template during this phase of processing.

Afterwards, a thermal treatment, or firing process, is often necessary in order to favour further polycondensation and enhance mechanical properties and structural stability via final sintering, densification, and grain growth. One of the distinct advantages of using this methodology as opposed to the more traditional processing techniques is that densification is often achieved at a much lower temperature.

The precursor sol can be either deposited on a substrate to form a film (e.g., by dip-coating or spin coating), cast into a suitable container with the desired shape (e.g., to obtain monolithic ceramics, glasses, fibers, membranes, aerogels), or used to synthesize powders (e.g., microspheres, nanospheres). The sol-gel approach is a cheap and low-temperature technique that allows the fine control of the product's chemical composition. Even small quantities of dopants, such as organic dyes and rare-earth elements, can be introduced in the sol and end up uniformly dispersed in the final product. It can be used in ceramics processing and manufacturing as an investment casting material, or as a means of

producing very thin films of metal oxides for various purposes. Materials derived by this technique have a wide variety of application in optics, electronics, energy, space etc.

The advantages of sol-gel methods are:

- ★ Capacity of sintering at low temperatures, between 200-600°C.
- ★ Synthesize high purity materials
- ★ Product homogeneity.
- ★ Good rheostat above powder particle shape and size and size distribution.
- ★ Easiness of manufacturing multi-component materials.
- ★ No particular apparatus with low price.

The synthesis of titanium dioxide nanoparticles is done by sol-gel method.

1.3 Applications

The capability of materials to radically modify their characteristics at the nanoscale has enabled the development of novel gadgets, sensors, and consumer items that perform far better than previously feasible. We know that nanoparticles have allowed us to create new goods that would not have been conceivable with bulk materials. Rapid development in the synthesis and understanding of nanomaterials in just a few years has led to their massive entry into the global market. Energy, automobiles, sports and toys, textiles, cosmetics, medical area, agriculture and food, domestic appliances, space, defense, and engineering are some of the fields that nanomaterials have entered or are soon to enter.

1.3.1 Medical Field

Nanotechnology is causing a massive change in biotechnology and medicine. Because of their tiny size and wide range of nanomaterials from noble to extremely reactive, nanoparticles may be used for diagnostics in the laboratory as well as therapies, since nanoparticles can be injected, breathed, or digested for various treatments. As previously

said, they may also be created in various forms such as spheres, wires, rods, tubes, or core-shell so that functional molecules can be connected inside or outside as needed to provide medication delivery or molecular recognition. Gold and silver compositions have been employed in traditional remedies.

When employed correctly, nanoparticles may be good heat or light absorbers as well as magnetically active. Nanotechnology is used in medical imaging, medication delivery, early cancer and tumor detection and destruction, surgery, wound healing, cardiology, Alzheimer and Parkinson therapy, diabetes treatment, dentistry, vision and hearing prosthesis, body implants, and other fields. This section attempts to explain how nanotechnology is assisting in the fields of imaging, medication delivery, cancer therapy, tissue welding, and bone and muscle treatment.

1.3.2 Agriculture and Foods

Food is a basic necessity for everyone, whether they live in a developed, developing, or underdeveloped country. As a result, the significance of agriculture is self-evident. After cultivation and manufacturing, agricultural raw goods require processing and adequate packaging before reaching customers. Nanotechnology has emerged in the last decade not only to increase production but also to minimize the use of numerous inputs like as pesticides, herbicides, and water.

The majority of agricultural nanotechnology research is concerned with sensing soil conditions, plant development, and providing a sufficient number of fertilizers, insecticides, or herbicides as needed. This might aid in the crop's correct and economic growth. Efficient and clever sensors are definitely required (a smart sensor would detect the presence of a disease and discharge a suitable amount of pesticide/herbicide). This is accomplished through 'precision farming,' which employs computers, global positioning systems (GPS), and remote sensing. This array of sensors will need to be distributed across the fields. Some of these concepts are still in their infancy, but scientists want to make them a reality.

Food firms are utilizing some novel nanotechnology ideas. Omega-3 fatty acids are known to lower blood clotting, platelet aggregation, insulin sensitivity in diabetic people, obesity, and help inhibit cancer development. Omega-3 fatty acids are abundant in fish (tuna and others), soyabean, tofu, and other foods. The odor of tuna fish oil is harsh and unpleasant, making it difficult to consume. The tuna fish oil was enclosed in a biocompatible capsule that explodes only after reaching the stomach. Nutritional bioavailability can be enhanced by employing nano self-assemblies of micelles. The nutrients enter the bloodstream from the stomach and become accessible. The technique is used to lower cholesterol, and it might also be used to give vitamins. A business developed a nano product that not only decreases the amount of energy required for cooking but also increases the life of the oil used in deep frying.

Packaging is critical for storing food for long periods of time as well as transporting it across large distances. A business employed SiO₂ nanoparticles to create airtight wrappers that keep food fresher for longer. Nano plastic wrappers are made with zinc oxide nanoparticles as catalysts, which are naturally antibacterial, UV and temperature resistant, and fire-proof. To retain the purity, flavor, and shelf life of the beer, nylon-based nanocomposites are utilized to create a barrier for CO₂ and O₂. The food preservation and packaging business is emphasizing the use of nano capsules within so that flavor and odor are activated only when utilized.

Colors and nutrients are also introduced only when the product is opened or consumed. Until then, capsules are inactive. It is also feasible to affix colour strips to determine whether or not the food is safe to eat. This might be useful for food containers at large malls. In summary, a number of revolutions using nanotechnology are taking place in agriculture and food supply.

1.3.3 Energy

Because of the great efficiency and cost effectiveness of nanomaterials, nanotechnology is predicted to play a key role in the sector of 'energy.' There is a lot of research being done to produce hydrogen fuel by splitting water (H₂O) with sunlight in the presence of nanomaterials (photocatalysts). Available hydrogen can really be an excellent source of fuel for autos and other modes of mobility. However, storing hydrogen is a difficult task since it often catches fire. Carbon nanotubes, a kind of nanomaterial, are being studied for their possible application as hydrogen storage materials. Carbon nanotubes are now quite expensive, but scientists are working to develop low-cost methods of producing them in huge quantities, which would be beneficial.

1.3.4 Cosmetics

Cosmetics also benefit from nanoparticles. Liposomes, solid lipid nanoparticles, and nanoemulsions, in addition to gold, silver, copper, platinum, and metal oxide nanoparticles such as zinc oxide, alumina, silica, and titanium oxide, have been found to be used in the formulations of various cosmetics such as face creams, lipsticks, body sprays, hair care products, sunscreens, and so on. Nanoparticle-based creams are recommended due to their small size since they can be applied sparingly and do not create any gaps between them. This results in a smooth look. Small particles in certain creams scatter light in such a manner that the appearance of wrinkles is reduced. Some nanoparticles can also penetrate deep into the skin and aid in the healing of skin problems such as wrinkles.

White sunscreens were traditionally utilised, but TiO₂ and ZnO-based sunscreens are transparent, considerably thinner than white screens, and perform better by blocking UV rays and protecting the face. Some lotions contain silver nanoparticles that can destroy germs while also providing protection. Nano-based dyes and colours are skin-safe and may be used in hair treatments or gels. Although nano-based cosmetics are becoming increasingly popular, some research on the effect of nano-cosmetics on human bodies indicates that some nanoparticles can be harmful to the human body.

1.3.5 Textiles

The textile industry is also quite interested in nanoparticles. There is certain clothing that have the appearance of synthetic fibre yet the feel of cotton. Nanotechnology has produced special threads and colours used in the textile industry. Nanotechnology-made clothing would not require ironing or regular washing. In fact, several businesses use silver nanoparticles in washing machines to keep garments germ-free. The use of silver in washing or directly in textiles ensures a germ-free environment, which is required for bandages, medical instruments, and child care goods. The use of extremely fluorescent colours derived from nano semiconductors is one option, but adjusting the spacing between the particles or the size of the nanoparticles woven into the fibre can also modify the colour.

There are other demonstrations of the notion that by weaving or integrating solar cells into clothing, enough electricity may be created to charge mobile phones, play MP3s, or other devices. To make a wearable computer, polymer transistors and other passive electronics can be woven in. Masks or even stylish clothing can be created that either catch pollutants or release pesticides when needed to kill, for example, mosquitoes. As a result, there is lots of potential to create innovative wearable textile designs. Self-cleaning carpets or tapestries that remove coffee or tea stains are already on the market. As a result, the field of textile research is producing fresh thoughts and helpful nano research.

1.3.6 Domestic Appliances

Refrigerators, air purifiers or air conditioners, and water purifiers all make use of silver nanoparticles. Silver has long been recognised to have antimicrobial properties. That is why it has long been used as a utensil material. However, new study has revealed that silver nanoparticles are far more effective and require just a little amount of them. As a result,

some manufacturers use specific nanoparticles to line refrigerators, air conditioners, and even washing machines.

Food in refrigerators can stay fresher and prevent fungal development for a longer period of time than food in regular refrigerators. Clothes washed in washing machines coated with silver nanoparticles are said to be sterile for approximately a month. This should come in handy in hospitals. Air conditioners and water filters using silver nanoparticles are also said to provide benefits and are being marketed at a low cost. Some building blocks, such as window materials, may be based on nanoparticles. Using proper window materials such as aerogels, which are very insulating but can be made transparent for window purposes, one may maintain the internal temperature of the home while decreasing heating/cooling impacts caused by outside weather. Self-cleaning glasses are also excellent for cleaning windows. Some window coatings can also be used to change the inside illumination of homes. Dye sensitised solar cells can be used to enhance the aesthetics of modern design while also meeting the local power requirements of a house or structure. As a result, nanomaterials are extremely beneficial.

1.3.7 Automobiles

An automobile is composed of several parts and materials. Its body and numerous structural sections are built of steel, various alloys, rubbers, plastics, and other materials. The body structure should be sturdy, non-deformable or stiff, and of the desired shape and size. It is well known that nanotube composites have more mechanical strength than steel. Composites that can replace steel are being developed. Nanotube synthesis is currently not commercially viable, but efforts are being undertaken to make them so that they may be employed on a big scale. Fine particles are sprayed onto automobiles. Nanoparticle paints produce a thin, appealing covering that is smooth and non-scratchable. Some study is being conducted to investigate the feasibility of using a low voltage to alter the colour of the automobile as requested.

Special window glass materials are available. It is possible to use self-cleaning' glass, which eliminates the need to wash the windows with water. Self-cleaning glass may be created by dissolving a tiny quantity of titania (TiO₂) nanoparticles in it while melting together its other constituents such as silica (SiO₂), CaO, Ba₂O₃, and so on. Titania may dissociate biological dust in the presence of UV radiation from the sun. It may tumble down or just disappear once detached. Even drips of water on glass create a foggy appearance. However, TiO₂-containing glass may equally disperse water, providing clean vision. As a result, nanotechnology may become one of the most important technologies for the automotive industry. What is being discussed for cars may equally be applicable to other automobiles.

1.3.8 Sports and Toys

Nanotechnology is already used in sports equipment and toys. Tennis balls made of nanoclay may better fill holes and trap air pressure within. This extends the life of the balls. Some international organisations have agreed to use such balls in their events. Carbon is used to make high-quality tennis racquets. Such racquets must be light in weight and durable or strong. Carbon nanotube composites might be used as a high strength, low weight material for racquets.

Balls and other equipment made of nanomaterials can also be used in other games. The toy business has also been ideally positioned to adopt nanotechnology. Children appreciate doll eye movements, robot motions, and so on, but they look extremely brisk. The toy business is currently using nanotechnology-based motors to make body part movements more smooth, quick, and natural-looking.

1.3.9 Space, Defence and Engineering

Scientists in space and defence are also attempting to use nanoparticles as alternative materials to replace traditional materials. Aerogels are nano porous materials with very low density (i.e., materials having small nanosized pores in them). Aerogels may be made from

a variety of materials. Their density ranges between 0.01-0.8 g/cm³. This density is comparable to that of iron, which is 7.8 g/cm³. As a result, one may gain a sense of how light aerogels are. Naturally, it is excellent for reducing weight in aerospace and defence applications. Aerogels may also be used to make particularly low weight suits, coats, and other clothing because they are poor heat conductors. Even certain difficult-to-manufacture high-temperature materials can be manufactured at lower temperatures utilizing nanomaterials.

Solar energy is mostly utilised in space to power satellites and spacecraft. At air mass zero, some of the solar cells now in use have an efficiency of 30%. (AM0). Some solar cells are reaching 40 percent efficiency. However, lowering the weight of materials used in solar cells remains an issue. Future spacecrafts may be powered by luminous dye sensitised nanoparticle-based or nanoparticle-based solar cell arrays, according to speculation.

1.4 TiO₂ Nanoparticles

Titanium dioxide nanoparticles, also called ultrafine titanium dioxide or nanocrystalline titanium dioxide or microcrystalline titanium dioxide, are particles of titanium dioxide (TiO₂) with diameters less than 100 nm. Nanosized particles of titanium dioxide tend to form in the metastable anatase phase, due to the lower surface energy of this phase, relative to the equilibrium rutile phase. Surfaces of ultrafine titanium dioxide in the anatase structure have photocatalytic sterilizing properties, which make it useful as an additive in construction materials, for example in antifogging coatings and self-cleaning windows.

TiO₂ is a compound of great importance due to its remarkable catalytic and distinctive semiconducting properties. It is also a chemically stable, non-toxic and biocompatible material. Nano TiO₂ is strong oxidizing agent with a large surface area and, hence, high photo-catalytic activities. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanoparticles have a high refractive index $n = 2.4$. It makes use in various applications, including medicines, coatings, inks, plastics, food, cosmetics, and textiles. The three crystalline phases are:

- Anatase (tetragonal)
- Rutile (tetragonal)
- Brookite (orthorhombic)

Due to their self-cleaning and anti-fogging properties they are widely applied in the preparation of fabrics, windows & anti-fogging automobile mirrors. TiO₂ also acts as sanitizer.

Manufacturing TiO₂ nanoparticles utilizes sol-gel, flame hydrolysis, co-precipitation, impregnation, and chemical vapor deposition processes. In particular, researchers are interested in the biosynthesis of titanium dioxide nanoparticles because it is a cost-effective, environmentally benign, and repeatable method.

Of the three common TiO₂ polymorphs (crystal forms), TiO₂ nanoparticles are produced in the rutile & anatase forms. The TiO₂ nanoparticles are transparent rather than white compared to large TiO₂ particles. The unique features of TiO₂ include electronic and short diffusion path. Generally, TiO₂ nanomaterials are wide band gap semiconductors containing E_g -values ranging from 3.0 to 3.2 eV with high absorption in the UV region. Ultraviolet absorption characteristics are dependent from the crystal size of titanium dioxide and ultrafine particles has strong absorption against both ultraviolet-A (320-400 nm) and ultraviolet-B (280-320 nm) radiation. Light absorption in the ultraviolet range occurs because of the presence of strongly bound excitons. The wavefunction of these excitons has a two-dimensional character and extends on the {001} plane.

In contrast, pigment-grade TiO₂ usually has a median particle size in the 200–300 nm range. Because TiO₂ powders contain a range of sizes, they may have a fraction of nanoscale particles even if the average particle size is larger. In turn ultrafine particles usually form agglomerates and particle size could be much larger than crystal size. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanoparticles are applicable to high performance technologies, as evident in current innovative applications. TiO₂ nanoparticles are therefore considered as superior functional

materials. Stoichiometric TiO₂ nanoparticles are categorized as active dielectric materials; nonstoichiometric nanoparticles are categorized as intrinsic semiconductor materials.

TiO₂ nanoparticles are proven effective in numerous optoelectronic applications. Such predominant phenomena are related to superior optoelectronic properties: high dielectric constant, high transmission coefficient, and high breakdown strength. TiO₂ nanoparticles are also beneficial to several photovoltaic applications. Such predominant phenomena are related to sufficient photoreactive properties.

1.4.1 Application of TiO₂

★ Photocatalytic Application

Photocatalysis is the chemical reaction that occurs when light strikes a light-sensitive chemical molecule. When light contacts titanium dioxide, a chemical reaction occurs in the local area, causing organic poisons, smells, and other substances to be broken down. Various semiconductor materials, including WO₃, ZrO₂, BiVO₄, Fe₂O₃, and NaTaO₃, have been created and demonstrated photocatalytic activity in recent years. Among them, TiO₂ is the most photocatalytically active substance employed for water splitting and organic material degradation. Because hydrogen is ecologically benign and pure, it is seen as the future fuel. Several research have been conducted in order to manufacture hydrogen by splitting water. First and foremost, Fujishima and Honda reported the photocatalytic splitting of water in the presence of a TiO₂ catalyst in 1972. These compounds have also been utilised to eliminate germs in water treatment and cancer cells.

By the absorption of photon $h\nu_1$, the photocatalytic mechanism is initiated manufacturing an electron-hole pair on the surface of TiO₂ nanoparticle. An electron is encouraged to the conduction band (CB) with formation of a positive hole with the valence band (VB). One or more radicals or intermediate species involved in this photodecomposition process play a crucial role in the photocatalytic mechanisms of reaction. The different factors play significant roles in controlled photocatalytic activities of semiconductors. With constant

adsorbents density on the surface, the semiconductors having large surface area led to faster reactions on the surface.

The size of titanium dioxide particles is much correlated to the fraction of surface located atoms. Due to the decrease in particles dimensions, the atomic fraction enhancing the catalytic activities on the surface increases. The band gap energy depends on the size of nanoparticle. It increases with decreasing nanoparticle sizes, which can be exploited in the optimization of redox potential. The electrons in transmission band and the holes in valence band allow photo-redox reactions easily. For high photocatalytic activity, the band gap permits only UV light to be proficiently used. Kormann and colleagues investigated the decomposition of 2-propanol using different sizes of TiO₂ nanoparticles. The authors observed that photocatalytic activities of 7.0 nm particles were 1.6 times better than 15–30 nm size.

Wang et al. studied the decomposition of chloroform by TiO₂ nanoparticles. They prepared TiO₂ nanoparticles with different size particles and observed the best size of TiO₂ nanoparticles for chloroform photocatalytic decomposition. By decreasing particle size from 21 to 11 nm, an enhancement in activity was observed. Contrarily, by reducing to 6 nm, the activity decreased completely. The authors concluded that the optimal particle size was about 10 nm for this reaction. In different types of TiO₂ nanomaterials, TiO₂ nanorods, mesoporous TiO₂ and nanotubes have revealed high photocatalytic performances under the appropriate circumstances. Rhodamine B was oxidized by mesoporous TiO₂ by Peng *et al.* On the oxidation reaction of desired materials, TiO₂ mesoporous showed significant activity. The nanotubes of TiO₂ treated with H₂SO₄ solutions were prepared by Yang *et al.* The authors observed that the TiO₂ nanotubes treated with different concentration of H₂SO₄ solutions showed photocatalytic activities for degradation of acid orange II. It was due to small particles having high specific surface areas of TiO₂ nanotubes after treated with H₂SO₄ solution.

★ Photovoltaic Applications

Dye sensitized solar cells have involved much consideration as reformative low- priced substitutes to usual solid- state devices. A DSSC composed a nanoporous film prepared from mesoporous oxide layer of anatase TiO_2 . Firstly, through a transparent conducting oxide (TCO) electrode, cell is illuminated where TiO_2 is deposited. Into the metal oxide conduction band, photo excited dye molecules insert electrons. I^-/IO_3^- couple acts as redox species in the electrolyte reducing the oxidized dye molecules back to their inventive state. Overall, the device produces electric power from light. The surface of nanoporous TiO_2 film is bounded by more cations than the electrons. Henceforth, electron transport mechanism is measured to be purely diffusive.

★ Pharmaceutical Applications

Titanium dioxide photocatalyst often involves sterilization and virus restraint due to its ability to damage cell membranes, solidify virus proteins, control virus activation, and capture infectious particles. It has been shown to eliminate 99.97% of microorganisms.

Coliform, green suppuration bacillus, golden grape coccus, mildew, suppuration fungus, and other bacteria are examples of targets that TiO_2 can kill. For example, studies have demonstrated the sterilizing ability of titanium dioxide using coliform and golden grape coccus; a population of 3.3105 coliforms and 3.2105 golden grape coccus were reduced to ten after 24 hours of reaction.

★ Waste Water Treatment

TiO_2 nanoparticles are ideal for wastewater treatment because of their low cost, corrosion resistance, and overall stability. They can be used as solid-phase extraction (SPE) packing material to preconcentrate and extract heavy metals from water for surface water remediation.

Diazinon is an organophosphate insecticide that is found in groundwater and is classed as a relatively harmful toxin (Class II by the World Health Organization). Ultraviolet light and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) nanoparticles doped with iron showed 98.58 % diazinon removal efficacy. Additionally, TiO₂ nanoparticles have a vital role in removing xenobiotic chemicals from wastewater, such as pesticides, dyes, and hazardous substances.

★ Agricultural Applications of TiO₂

TiO₂ nanoparticles have been shown to boost the rate of photosynthesis in spinach crops. In other species, more pigmentation was detected in Zea mays sprayed with nano TiO₂ during the reproductive stages of the plant, leading to increased crop production. When applied to tomato plants as an aerosol, TiO₂ nanoparticles were found to be more effective at increasing photosynthesis and lycopene content than TiO₂ nanoparticles used as a soil amendment.

Drug Delivery Systems for Cancer Therapy

Traditional chemotherapy cancer treatment can have catastrophic effects on cells due to their toxic nature. As a result, the focus has been placed on how nanotechnology can be used to diagnose and treat cancer. Currently, the most significant challenge to overcome is reducing the side effects of nanotechnology-enabled drug systems.

Some strategies have shown promising results, involving controlling the number of drugs released to the cell or targeting specific cells and delivering medications to them.

1.5 Review of Literature

- 1) Smith L, Kuncic Z, Ostrikov K, et al. Investigates the potential of TiO₂ nanoparticles as a potential contrast agent for dual-mode imaging and therapy. They measured the effects of each of these agents on dose delivered by a kilovoltage X-ray therapy unit and imaged nanoparticle-impregnated volumes with a clinical CT scanner to

determine their image contrast properties. Preliminary results for titanium dioxide nanoparticles as potential dual mode imaging and therapy enhancement agents indicate they are a promising candidate for image contrast in computed tomography.

- 2) Harada A, Ono M, Yuba E, et al. successfully prepared TiO₂ NP-entrapped PIC micelles by mixing a TiO₂ NP dispersion and PAA-g-PEG. The results obtained here indicate that TiO₂ NP-entrapped micelles have potential utility in SDT. In addition, TiO₂ has versatile properties including chemical inertness toward biological systems, low cost, and easy preparation of stable suspensions with a nanoparticulate form.
- 3) Dorian A. H. Hanaor Charles C. Sorrell present work aims to clarify the differences between the two main polymorphs of titanium dioxide, the nature of the anatase to rutile transformation, and the principles of controlling phase composition through the inhibition or promotion of the transformation of anatase to rutile. At all temperatures and pressures, rutile is the stable phase of TiO₂. Anatase is metastable but it can be considered to be kinetically stabilised at lower temperatures. Although rutile is the more stable phase from a thermodynamic point of view, anatase frequently is the product phase in the synthesis of TiO₂ owing to its less constrained structure and consequent enhanced kinetics of formation
- 4) Li et al. investigated the distribution and effects of TiO₂ NPs (3 nm; 13.2 mg/kg; once a week for 4 weeks) in mice. They suggested that TiO₂ NPs might pass through the blood–brain barrier.
- 5) Ferin et al. monitored pulmonary retention of TiO₂ FPs and NPs in rats after a single intratracheal instillation or 12-week inhalation of different sizes of TiO₂ particles (12, 21, 230, and 250 nm). They found that migration of particles to the interstitium appeared to be related to the particle size, the delivered dose, and the delivered dose rate. In addition, both acute instillation and sub-chronic inhalation studies showed that TiO₂ NPs (20 nm) at equivalent masses access the pulmonary interstitium to a larger extent than TiO₂ FPs (250 nm).

- 6) Jugan et al. has shown that spherical TiO₂ NPs (12–140 nm; both anatase and rutile) can induce single strand breaks, oxidative lesions to DNA and oxidative stress in A549 cells. They also showed that TiO₂ NPs impair the cell's ability to repair DNA by deactivation of both nucleotide excision repair (NER) and base excision repair (BER) pathways.
- 7) A recent study by Woodruff et al. found that TiO₂ NPs (10 nm anatase spheres; non-coated; 0-200 µg/ml; 24 h) were not genotoxic under the conditions of the Ames test and Comet assay in the thymidine kinase heterozygote (TK6) cell lines. There was no significant DNA damage or oxidative DNA damage observed.
- 8) Adawiya J. Haider, Zainab N. Jameel, Imad H. M. Al-Hussain found that the anatase phase NPs can be utilized in paint due to the photocatalytic properties of TiO₂ that lead to self-cleaning surfaces and materials in an experiment of TiO₂ NPs with two phases (anatase and rutile) and with different concentrations were mixed under magnetic stirring for two hours at 50°C until a homogenous mixture with pH in the range of (6-7) was achieved.
- 9) João Victor Marques Zoccal, Fábio de Oliveira Arouca, José Antonio Silveira Gonçalves in their experiment concluded as the results of thermogravimetric analysis, thermal differential analysis and infrared analysis showed the degradation of the polymer and the formation of the phases of anatase and rutile TiO₂ crystal. The analysis of X-ray diffraction showed the formation of anatase and rutile phases and the enlargement of peak proved the presence of nanoparticles of TiO₂ powder. The micrographs of TiO₂ powder showed the formation of clusters with heterogeneous disordered structure without structural definition.
- 10) M. Hussain, R. Ceccarelli, D.L. Marchisio, D. Fino, N. Russo* , F. Geobaldo In this work, novel TNP was successfully synthesized on large scale by sol–gel method using VR with optimized operating parameters and conditions. Characterization comparison was done with the synthesized TSC and commercially purchased TiO₂ using different analysis techniques in detail. The obtained results in this study are

very encouraging, showing further way for optimizations and promising applications especially in the photocatalysis of VOCs and many more.

11) Kristina Fischer, Alina Gawel, David Rosen, was directly synthesized Non-agglomerated TiO₂ nanoparticles via low-temperature dissolution-precipitation on a microfiltration PES membrane with different crystallinities and varying crystal composition, including anatase, brookite, and rutile.

1.6 Reference:

1. Michael F. Ashby, Paulo J Ferreira, Daniel L Schodek – Nanomaterials, nanotechnology and design.
2. C Noguera, physics at oxide surface, Cambridge university.
3. H.H Kung, Transition Metal Oxides: Surface and Catalysis; Elsevier: Amsterdam
4. Dehradun P (2015) A review on nanoparticles—preparation and evaluation parameters.
5. Sulabha K. Kulkarni, Nanotechnology: Principles and Practices, Third Edition
6. Smith L, Kuncic Z, Ostrikov K (Ken), et al. Nanoparticles in Cancer Imaging and Therapy. *J. Nanomater.* 2012; 1–7
7. Harada A, Ono M, Yuba E, et al. Titanium dioxide nanoparticle-entrapped polyion complex micelles generate singlet oxygen in the cells by ultrasound irradiation for sonodynamic therapy. *Biomater. Sci.* 2013; 1:65–73
8. Fujiwara R, Luo Y, Sasaki T, et al. Cancer Therapeutic Effects of Titanium Dioxide Nanoparticles Are Associated with Oxidative Stress and Cytokine Induction. *Pathobiology.* 2015;82: 243–251
9. Selin Çeşmeli and Cigir Biray Avcı* Ege Universitesi Tip Fakultesi, Izmir, 35100 Turkey
10. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780128135860000018>
11. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B978012813586000002X>

Chapter 2

Experimental Techniques

2.1 Introduction

This chapter mainly focuses on the theory behind the characterization techniques for investigating different properties of the prepared samples. The thermal stability of the

sample is analysed using Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA). The structural characterization of the sample is done using X-ray Diffraction (XRD) and Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis (EDAX) technique. The optical properties of the samples are studied using UV-Visible (UV-Vis) and Photoluminescence (PL) Spectroscopy.

2.2 Thermal Analysis

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) is a technique used to determine the changes that occur to a specimen as a result of heating from room temperature to a certain high temperature. When both samples are heated in a furnace, TGA evaluates the weight loss that occurs as a function of temperature or time in contrast to an inert reference sample.

Thermogravimetric analysis may be used to identify the optimal calcination temperature of a sample. The size and crystallinity of nanoparticles are determined by the calcination temperature.

2.3 Structural Characterization

2.3.1 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

XRD is an important tool to investigate the crystalline structure of materials. The interatomic spacing in crystals is of the order of the wavelength of X-rays. So, a crystal can act as a three-dimensional grating for producing a diffraction pattern. When X-rays are incident on a crystal, their electric field components interact with atomic electrons in different parallel crystal planes and they undergo elastic scattering. X-rays scattered in certain specific directions get superposed to produce a diffraction pattern obeying Bragg's law represented by the relation,

$$2d \sin \theta = n\lambda \quad \dots\dots\dots$$

(2.1)

where d is the distance between adjacent crystal planes, θ the angle of diffraction, n the order of diffraction and λ the wavelength of incident monochromatic X-ray.

Fig:2.1 X-Ray Diffraction

The scattered X-rays carry information about the arrangement of atoms within the crystal. Also, the intensity is found to depend on the inter-planar spacing and incident wave angle. The orderly arrangement of atoms produces intense peak. XRD pattern contains information regarding crystal structure and lattice parameters. Any stress or strain occurring to a material's crystal structure will be reflected in the peak position. The stress strain analysis can be performed to draw certain conclusions regarding the material properties. Modern X-ray diffractometer is equipped with computer programs to generate all information pertaining to a crystal.

In powder XRD, the sample is taken in fine powder form, and each powder particle is polycrystalline. The output of the XRD experiment is generally obtained as a plot of 2θ versus intensity of the diffracted beam. Average particle size D is calculated from the XRD plot using the Scherrer equation,

$$D = k\lambda / \beta \cos \theta \quad \dots\dots\dots(2.2)$$

where, k is a constant known as shape factor which is approximately 0.89 for spherical shape, λ is 1.5406 Å is the wavelength of Cu K_{α} radiation and β = the full width at half maximum of the peak at 2θ value. The crystal phase, crystal planes and unit cell parameters of the samples can be determined by comparing the XRD pattern obtained with standard data files of the Joint Committee on Powder Diffraction Standards (JCPDS).

In the present work, XRD measurements are carried out using Bruker AXS D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer (step size = 0.020°, step time = 31.2 s) with CuK α (λ = 1.5406Å) radiation at room temperature operating at a voltage of 40 kV and filament current of 35 mA.

2.4 Optical Characterization

In this study, UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy and photoluminescence techniques are used for the optical characterization of samples.

2.4.1 UV - Vis Spectroscopy

UV-Vis spectroscopy is an analytical technique is used to measure the number of discrete wavelengths of UV or visible light absorbed or transmitted through a sample by comparing it with a reference or blank sample. It provides information about what is in the sample and at what concentration by analyzing the sample composition. It measures the attenuation of light which pass through under consideration sample or after reflecting from the sample. Also, we can measure the purity of sample by comparing it with a reference solution.

When UV-Visible light is passed through a material, certain wavelengths that are characteristic of the material are absorbed. The working of UV-visible spectrophotometer is based on the absorption of electromagnetic radiations by the sample in the ultraviolet, visible and near infrared range (200-1000 nm). Along with absorption, a certain part of the incident light gets reflected and another part gets transmitted. Measurements based on absorbance, reflectance and transmittance can be performed by selecting suitable modes of

operation of the instrument. The bandgap of the material is estimated by putting absorption coefficient α in the Tauc relation,

$$\alpha h\nu = A(h\nu - E_g)^n \quad \dots\dots\dots(2.3)$$

where A is a constant, $h\nu$, the photon energy and E_g , the bandgap. $n = 1/2$ for direct semiconductors. The band gap of the samples can be estimated by plotting $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ as a function of $h\nu$ and extrapolating linear region of the curve to absorption equal to zero.

The basic components of a spectrophotometer are the light source, sample holder, monochromator, detector and recorder. UV and visible light from the source are first collimated and then split into its component wavelengths using a monochromator. The light is divided into two beams by the beam splitter and one half of the beam passes through the sample. and other through the reference. The transmitted beams are detected, amplified and processed by the computer to obtain the spectrum.

Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy is used to measure the reflectance data of the powder samples. When the light beam traverses a sample, it may get reflected, transmitted or absorbed. The diffuse reflection reveals the part of the incident light beam scattered within the sample and comes back to the surface. The reflected component of the sample beam is collected by the integrating sphere and detected by the detector. Kubelka Munk transformation is employed to determine the absorption coefficients of the powder samples from the reflectance measurements.

Diffuse reflectance data are collected over the spectral range 200-800 nm using Shimadzu UV 2600 UV–Visible spectrophotometer. For the measurement, nanoparticles are pressed into a thick pellet in a sample holder and placed at the entrance port of the integrating sphere. Barium sulphate is used as the reference material for the calibration of reflectance scale.

2.4.2 Photoluminescence Spectroscopy (PL)

Photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy is a non-destructive technique which is used to study the physical and chemical properties of a given material by using photons to induce excited electronic states (photo-excitation of electrons into permissible excited states). The excess energy is released in the form of optical emission by radiative or non-radiative process and is the difference between the excited and equilibrium states of transition. Qualitative and quantitative information about chemical composition, structure, impurities, different intrinsic properties, surface defects, traps produced etc. can be understood by using the PL spectrum of a material. The energy corresponding to the emission peaks is given by,

$$E = h\nu = hc/\lambda \text{ in eV} \quad \dots\dots\dots(2.4)$$

where λ is the wavelength in nm corresponding to the emission peak.

Light from the source, a high-pressure Xenon arc lamp falls on the excitation monochromator, which transmits a narrow range centred about the selected excitation wavelength. The transmitted light passes through the sample cell causing fluorescent emission. The emission monochromator transmits light in a narrow range centred about the specified emission wavelength. The light finally falls on the detector which amplifies and creates a voltage that is proportional to the emitted intensity.

Horiba Scientific-Fluoromax4 spectrophotometer is used to record the PL spectra of the samples at room temperature with a spectral accuracy of 0.5 nm in the present study.

2.5 Reference:

1. P. J. Haines, Thermal Methods of Analysis. (Springer Netherlands, 1995).
2. C. Kittel, Introduction to solid state physics. (Wiley, 1976).
3. W. L. Bragg, presented at the Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society, 1913.
4. T. Varghese and K. Balakrishna, (New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers, 2011).
5. B. D. Cullity, Elements of X-ray diffraction, 2nd Edition ed. (Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, California, 1978).

6. J. Tauc, Amorphous and Liquid Semiconductors, 1 ed. (Plenum Press, New York, 1974).
7. <https://www.technologynetworks.com/analysis/articles/uv-vis-spectroscopy-principle-strengths-and-limitations-and-applications-349865#D1>
8. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/materials-science/photoluminescence>
9. <https://www.scimed.co.uk/education/what-is-x-ray-diffraction-xrd/>
10. [https://chem.libretexts.org/Courses/Franklin_and_Marshall_College/Introduction_to_Materials_Characterization_CHM_412_Collaborative_Text/Spectroscopy/Energy-Dispersive_X-ray_Spectroscopy_\(EDS\)#:~:text=This%20principle%20is%20known%20as,release%20energy%20as%20it%20relaxes.](https://chem.libretexts.org/Courses/Franklin_and_Marshall_College/Introduction_to_Materials_Characterization_CHM_412_Collaborative_Text/Spectroscopy/Energy-Dispersive_X-ray_Spectroscopy_(EDS)#:~:text=This%20principle%20is%20known%20as,release%20energy%20as%20it%20relaxes.)

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Introduction

The synthesis of Titanium dioxide nanoparticles by sol gel method and its transformation from anatase to rutile phase are described in this chapter. The thermal stability and the decomposition of synthesized materials are studied using thermogravimetric (TG) analysis. The structural characterization of the nanoparticles is done using X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique. The optical absorption of these nanoparticles is investigated using UV-Visible and photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopic methods.

3.2 Materials and Methods

All the chemicals used for the synthesis of titanium dioxide are of analytic reagent grade. The specific reagents used for the synthesis of titanium dioxide include titanium (IV)-n -

butoxide ($\text{Ti}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)_4$ or $\text{Ti}(\text{OBu})_4$), 97%, Sigma Aldrich), isopropyl alcohol ($(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHOH}$), 99%, Merck) and conc. HNO_3 (99.9%, Merck). Distilled water is used throughout the synthesis

3.3 Synthesis

The flowchart showing the scheme for the synthesis of TiO_2 is shown in Figure 3.1. The precursor solution is a mixture of 1:2 solution of titanium (IV)-n-butoxide ($\text{Ti}(\text{OBu})_4$) and isopropyl alcohol. This solution was then added drop wise into a solution of distilled water under stirring condition. The hydrolysis was performed at room temperature while stirring for 3hrs and a sol was formed. Finally, the formed sol was dried at 60°C for 20hrs to obtain TiO_2 powder. The obtained powder samples were then calcined for 3hrs in a furnace at 400 and 800°C .

Fig 3.1 Scheme of preparation of TiO_2 using sol-gel synthesis

3.4 Thermogravimetric Analysis

The thermal decomposition of the as prepared sample from the ambient temperature to 1000°C is done using thermogravimetric analysis and is shown in Fig 3.2.

Fig 3.2 TGA curve of TiO₂

The TG curve indicates that the weight loss of the as prepared sample occurred from 50^o to 400^oC. This may be related to the decomposition of the residual titanium butoxide and organic compounds. This suggests that the synthesized sample decomposed completely by 400^oC to become titanium dioxide.

3.5 XRD Analysis

XRD analysis has been carried out in the reflection mode using *Bruker AXS D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer* (step size = 0.020°, step time = 31.2 s, generator voltage = 40 kV, current = 35 mA) with Cu-K α 1 ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) radiation in 2θ range from 20 to 90°. The XRD patterns of calcined TiO₂ samples are illustrated in Figure 3.4 and 3.5.

Fig. 3.3 XRD patterns for anatase TiO₂ nanoparticles

The XRD patterns indicate that the structure of TiO₂ is anatase at a calcination temperature of 400°C and rutile at 800°C. The anatase phase identified at 2θ values of 25.357, 37.888, 48.024, 54.9 and 62.768 agrees with the standard XRD pattern (JCPDS files No. 21-1272). The peaks at 2θ values of 27.468, 36.095, 41.258, 44.076, 56.659 and 69.036 corresponds to the rutile phase of TiO₂, and is in agreement with the standard XRD pattern (JCPDS files No. 21-1276). Thus, a phase transition from anatase to rutile occurs when the calcination temperature is increased from 400°C to 800°C. The peak position of the samples and its correlation with Miller indices can be seen in Table 1.

Fig. 3.4 XRD patterns for rutile TiO₂ nanoparticles

Table 1: The peak position of the samples and its correlation with Miller indices.

Sample heated at 400°C			Sample heated at 800°C		
2 Theta (deg)	Miller indices	Phase	2 Theta (deg)	Miller indices	Phase
25.356	101	Anatase	27.468	110	Rutile
37.888	112		36.095	200	
48.024	200		41.258	111	
54.900	105		44.076	211	

62.768	204		56.659	220	
			69.036	301	

From this figure, it is observed that diffraction peaks become intense and their FWHM decreases on heating the sample from 400°C to 800°C, indicating an increase in crystallite size. The crystallite sizes of the samples are calculated from the line broadening of the diffraction peaks using Scherrer formula,

$$D = k\lambda / \beta \cos\theta \quad \dots\dots\dots(3.1)$$

where represents the average crystallite size, $k = 0.89$ (Scherrer constant), $\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$ (wavelength of the X-ray Cu $K\alpha$ radiation), θ the diffraction angle of the peak and β represents the full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the peaks. The values obtained were 11.3 and 58 nm for the anatase and rutile samples respectively. Geometric parameters of the samples are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Geometric parameters of TiO₂

Sample	2θ	FWHM	Average crystallite size (nm)
Anatase	25.356	0.72	11.3
	48.024	0.765	
Rutile	27.474	0.136	58
	36.116	0.162	

41.268	0.127
44.097	0.161

Fig. 3.6 XRD patterns of anatase and rutile phase of TiO₂ nanoparticles

3.6 UV-Visible Spectroscopy

UV-Vis absorption spectra of the samples were recorded in the wavelength range 200 – 800 nm from reflectance measurements using a *Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer UV 2600 model*.

Fig. 3.7 UV-Vis absorption spectra of anatase and rutile TiO₂ nanoparticles

UV-Vis absorption spectra of the samples are illustrated in Figure 3.7. Both the samples exhibit good absorption in the UV region followed by an absorption hump between 300 and 400 nm. The UV absorption corresponds to the electron transition from the valence band to the conduction band (band–band transition). The hump which is clearer for the rutile sample may be due to the presence of Ti³⁺ vacancies generated on annealing. A red shift is occurring during the phase transition from anatase to rutile.

Fig. 3.8 Tauc Plot of TiO₂ nanoparticles

Direct bandgap (E_d) of samples is determined by fitting absorption data to direct transition equation,

$$\alpha h\nu = E_d(h\nu - E_g)^{1/2} \quad \dots\dots\dots(3.2)$$

where α is optical absorption coefficient, $h\nu$ photon energy and a constant. Band gap of the samples have been measured by plotting as a function of photon energy $h\nu$ and extrapolating linear portion of the curve to absorption equal to zero. Figure 3.8 shows the $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs $h\nu$ graph of the TiO₂ samples. The band gap energy obtained for the anatase and rutile samples are 3.43 and 3.00 eV respectively. Generally, rutile owns a relatively narrower bandgap (around 3.05eV) compared to anatase phase and is also the most thermostable form of TiO₂.

3.7 PL Spectroscopy

Figure 3.9 illustrates the PL emission spectra for anatase and rutile phases of TiO_2 samples at room temperature. The samples exhibit a strong and wide PL signal from 400 to 500 nm and a shoulder peak at 377 nm with an excited wavelength of 300 nm. The shoulder peak corresponds to the direct recombination between electrons in conduction band and holes in valence band. The emission peak at 470 nm is related to the surface trap states. Both the samples exhibit similar type of PL signal with no significant change in the curve shape.

The emission intensity of anatase is higher than that of rutile sample. If the particle size is smaller, the oxygen vacancy content is large and hence absorption over UV and visible range increases. Annealing at higher temperature causes a decrease in defect centers thereby reducing the intensity of emission for the rutile phase.

Fig. 3.9 PL spectra of TiO_2 nanoparticles

3.8 References

1. K P Priyanka, S Joseph, A T Sunny and T Varghese Nanosystems: Phys. Chem. Maths. 4 218 (2013)
2. H Yang, K Zhang, R Shi, X Li, X Dong, Y Yu, J. Alloys Compd 413 (2006) 302–306
3. K. Nagaveni, G. Sivalingam, M. S. Hegde, G. Madras, J. Phys. Chem. B., 108 (2004) 20204; DOI: 10.1016/j.jssc.2011.05.036
4. M.M. Viana, V.F. Soares, N.D.S. Mohallem, Ceram. Int., 36 (2010) 2047–2053
5. A J Haider, R H Al-Anbari, G R Kadhim, C T Salame, Energy Procedia 119 (2017)332 – 345
6. K Thamaphat, P Limsuwan, B Ngotawornchai, Kasetsart J. (Nat. Sci.) 4(2008) 357 – 361
7. S.N. Karthick, K. Prabakar, A. Subramania, Ji-Tae Hong, Jin-Ju Jang, Hee-Je Kim, Powder Technology 205 (2011) 36–41
8. B. Choudhury, A. Choudhury, Physica E Low Dimens. Syst. Nanostruct., 56(2014), 364 - 371
9. N. Serpone, D. Lawless, R. Khairutdinov, J. Phys. Chem. 1995, 99, (45), 16646-16654.
10. S. Paul, A. Choudhury, Appl. Nanosci., 4 (2014) 839-847

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The present work describes the synthesis of titanium dioxide nanoparticles by sol-gel method and the study of the transition from anatase to rutile phase.

Sol-gel synthesis method has been successfully employed for the synthesis of titanium dioxide nanoparticles. The TGA studies show no weight loss for the sample after 400°C. Hence the as prepared samples are heated at 400 and 800°C for three hours.

The XRD patterns indicate that the structure of TiO₂ is anatase at a calcination temperature of 400°C and rutile at 800°C. The X-ray diffraction studies show an increase in the intensity of diffraction peaks, decrease in FWHM and increase in crystallite size. The crystallite size values obtained are 11.3 and 58 nm for the anatase and rutile samples respectively.

The optical absorption spectra of TiO₂ sample exhibited strong absorption in the UV region. A hump is observed between 300 and 400 nm which is clearer for the rutile sample. This may be due to the presence of Ti³⁺ vacancies generated on annealing. The band gap energy values obtained are 3.43 and 3.00 eV for the anatase and rutile samples respectively, in close agreement with the values obtained in other studies.

The samples exhibit a strong and wide PL signal from 400 to 500 nm and a shoulder peak at 377 nm with an excited wavelength of 300 nm. Both the samples exhibit similar type of PL signal with no significant change in the curve shape.

The emission intensity of anatase is higher than that of rutile sample. If the particle size is smaller, The larger oxygen vacancy content for smaller samples enhances the UV and visible range absorption. But annealing at higher temperature causes a decrease in defect centres thereby reducing the intensity of emission for the rutile phase.

